

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2351163
UDC Classification: 339.138: 378.4
JEL Classification: D23, H12

METHODICAL BASES OF RESEARCH AND ANALYSIS OF STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS AND PROSPECTS FOR DEVELOPMENT OF DOMESTIC INSTITUTIONS OF HIGHER EDUCATION

МЕТОДИЧНІ ЗАСАДИ ДОСЛІДЖЕННЯ ТА АНАЛІЗУВАННЯ СТРАТЕГІЧНИХ НАПРЯМІВ ТА ПЕРСПЕКТИВ РОЗВИТКУ ВІТЧИЗНЯНИХ ЗВО

Myroslava I. Bublyk, Doctor of Economics, Professor
Lviv Polytechnic National University, Lviv, Ukraine
ORCID: 0000-0003-2403-0784
Scopus Author ID: 6602604353
Email: my.bublyk@gmail.com

Liliya V. Zhuk, Doctor of Philosophy, Associate Professor
Lviv Polytechnic National University, Lviv, Ukraine
ORCID: 0000-0001-7299-2705
Scopus Author ID: 6701396496
Email: liliia.v.zhuk@lpnu.ua

Nataliya Ya. Petryshyn, PhD in Economics, Associate Professor
Lviv Polytechnic National University, Lviv, Ukraine
ORCID: 0000-0003-4642-1778
Scopus Author ID: 57202220268
Email: natalya.petryshyn@gmail.com

Nataliya I. Duliaba, PhD in Economics, Associate Professor
Lviv Polytechnic National University, Lviv, Ukraine
ORCID: 0000-0002-4377-874X
Email: d_natka@ukr.net
Recieved 11.08.2018

Бублик М.І., Жук Л.В., Петришин Н.Я., Дуляба Н.І. Методичні засади дослідження та аналізування стратегічних напрямів та перспектив розвитку вітчизняних ЗВО. Науково-методична стаття.

Розроблено інноваційні засади дослідження та аналізування стратегічних напрямів та перспектив розвитку вітчизняних закладів вищої освіти. Запропоновано структурно-логічну модель. Визначено мету, об'єкт, методи дослідження, особливості формування вибірки, напрями дослідження та аналізування. З метою формування стратегічних напрямів та перспектив розвитку вітчизняних закладів вищої освіти проведено анкетне опитування експертів. Запропоновано змістове наповнення кожного окремого напрямку дослідження, що дало змогу забезпечити використання запропонованого інноваційного підходу та здійснити правильний вибір варіанту відповіді визначеними респондентами опитування. За результатами проведеного дослідження розроблено матрицю SWOT-аналізу. Сформовано відповідне інформаційне забезпечення для формування стратегічних напрямів та перспектив розвитку вітчизняних закладів вищої освіти.

Ключові слова: стратегічний розвиток, стратегічні цілі, стратегічні завдання, заклади вищої освіти, анкетування, експертне опитування, репутація ЗВО

Bublyk M.I., Zhuk L.V., Petryshyn N.Ya., Duliaba N.I. Methodical bases of research and analysis of strategic directions and prospects for development of domestic institutions of higher education. Scientific and methodical article.

Innovative principles of research and analysis of strategic directions and prospects of development of domestic institutions of higher education are developed. The structural-logical model is proposed. The purpose, object, methods of research, peculiarities of the formation of the sample, directions of research and analysis are determined. In order to form strategic directions and prospects for the development of domestic institutions of higher education, a questionnaire survey of experts was conducted. The content of each separate study direction is proposed, which will enable to use the proposed innovative approach and make the correct choice of the answer variant by the respondents determined by the survey. According to the results of the study, a SWOT analysis matrix was developed. Appropriate informational support has been formed for forming strategic directions and prospects for the development of domestic higher education institutions.

Keywords: strategic development, strategic goals, strategic objectives, institutions of higher education, questionnaires, expert polls, reputation of IHE

Modern conditions of functioning put forward new requirements for the activities of institutions of higher education. A highly competitive environment requires the formation of a new approach to the strategic development of domestic higher education institutions (HEI), which will be aimed at continuous improvement and qualitative transformations in the educational, scientific spheres, international positioning. The success of the activities of domestic institutions of higher education and their further development directly depends on correctly selected strategic guidelines.

Analysis of recent research and publications

Strategic analysis of the activities of institutions of higher education and the system of higher education is devoted to many scientific works of domestic and foreign scholars. In the writings of national scholars [1-7]: Gladchenko M.M., Pinyak I., Pokryskina L., Ponomarchuk N., Totskaya O.L., Shevchenko L.S., Yarmosh O. The problems of SWOT-analysis are investigated. higher education and higher education institutions; the problems of forming the reputation of higher educational institutions as a priority strategic reference point are set out. In their writings, the authors of the paper [8-10] justify an innovative way of achieving competitive advantage for organizations that have benchmarking. The effectiveness of educational development through strategic benchmarking was studied by foreign scholars Martin M., Sauvageo S., Gourishankar V., Sai Lokachari P., Koller M., Salzberger T. in their writings [11-13]. By studying the strategies of the development of domestic universities [14-21], it is easy to see that research and analysis of strategic directions and prospects for the development of leading HEIs (leaders both at the world and national level) is a special place in these strategies.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

For a clear understanding, the review of publications indicates the insufficient disclosure of the problem of research and analysis of strategic directions and prospects for the development of domestic HEIs. The authors pay little attention to the issues of specification of the research areas, the formation of a sample, the composition of information to be obtained in the course of such research, as well as the methods whose application will be most expedient in the study and analysis of strategic directions and prospects for the development of domestic HEIs.

The aim of the article is to develop methodological principles for research and analysis of strategic directions and prospects of development of domestic HEI in order to identify problems in this area. In order to realize the research objective, the following tasks need to be solved: 1) to develop a structural and logical model of research and analysis of strategic directions and prospects of development of domestic HEIs; 2) determine the purpose, object, methods of research, the peculiarities of the formation of the sample, the directions of research and analysis; 3) to identify the strengths and weaknesses, threats and opportunities of domestic higher education institutions and form a matrix of SWOT-analysis; 4) on the basis of the results of the study, form the main strategic directions and prospects for the development of domestic institutions of higher education.

The main part

The analysis of the development of educational and scientific activity of institutions of higher education, which was carried out by the authors in the work [22], allowed to form a goal and task of more deeply research and analysis of strategic directions and prospects of development of domestic HEIs. In this case, the object of research and analysis is the domestic HEI, their activities, strategic directions and prospects for development. Recommended methods of research and analysis: questionnaires, SWOT-analysis. The sample is formed according to the probabilistic procedure, the members of the general population are: the heads of the institutional level of management of the HEI, the directors of the institutes and the heads of the departments; employers; students. The identified areas of research are: the main factors in the formation of the reputation of HEI; Generally recognized scientific schools of HEI; determinants of strategic development of HEI; Strategic measures to strengthen positions in international and domestic systems for evaluating HEI; the strengths and weaknesses of the HEI; opportunities and threats of the development of the HEI; priority strategic directions of the development of HEI. The developed structural-logical model of research and analysis of strategic directions and prospects of development of domestic HEIs is presented in fig. 1

Within the framework of this study, it is recommended to conduct a standardized survey of experts, namely, managers of the institutional higher level of management of the HEI, since the formation of strategic directions of development and strategic guidelines of activity is within the competence of the higher management of institutions of higher education. For the purpose of obtaining no less important information regarding the reputation of the HEI, it is recommended that surveys be conducted among students and employers.

In the course of the research, it is necessary to determine the general population and the sample size. The research tool is a questionnaire. When conducting a questionnaire survey of the heads of the institutional level of the HEI, the directors of the institutes and the heads of the departments in the context of research and analysis of strategic directions and prospects of development of domestic HEIs, it is recommended to formulate a list of issues in the context of certain areas of research. In this case, the following material describes the possible answers that will be selected by the respondents in the context of the questions in the questionnaire.

The main factors in the formation of the reputation of the HEI: 1) the quality of education; 2) the quality of scientific research; 3) Innovation of educational technologies; 4) personnel potential; 5) information potential; 6) material and technical potential; 7) qualitative composition of students; 8) student motivation; 9) the quality of the material and technical base and educational and methodological support of scientific activity; 10) the quality of the material and technical base and educational and methodological support of the educational process; 11) other.

Generally recognized HEI science schools are an important factor in shaping the reputation of a higher education institution, its positive image and global recognition. Scientific schools form the style of scientific

activity in a particular field, as well as a special program concept, which is the basis for solving scientific problems.

Fig. 1. Structural-logical model of research and analysis of strategic directions and prospects of development of domestic HEI

Source: compiled by the authors

Determinants of strategic development of the HEI: 1) scientific activity; 2) demand for graduates from domestic and foreign employers; 3) cooperation with universities in the direction of developing international academic cooperation; 4) cooperation with universities in the direction of developing international scientific cooperation; 5) the reputation of the university according to experts' assessments in international and domestic systems for evaluating HEI; 6) reputation of the university among employers as education customers; 7) university reputation among employers as education investors; 8) the authority of scientific and scientific-pedagogical workers; 9) the number of publications in the publications included in Scopus or Web of Science; 10) provision of educational services for the first, second, third educational qualification levels; 11) other.

Strategic measures to strengthen positions in international and domestic systems for assessing HEI: 1) strengthening the publication activity of scientific and pedagogical workers; 2) the involvement of leading foreign teachers in the work of the HEI; 3) increasing the academic mobility of scientific and scientific and pedagogical workers; 4) participation in international grants, international educational and scientific projects; 5) the entry of scientific editions of HEI into the science-based bases of Scopus or Web of Science; 6) attraction of funds for research work on general and special funds; 7) the Internet presence of structural units of the university; 8) search of new perspective scientific directions taking into account the priority directions of development of science and technology; 9) development of international cooperation, research and project implementation as part of international teams, strengthening of the international component in conducting fundamental research; 10) other.

Strengths of the HEI: 1) high qualification of scientific and scientific and pedagogical workers; 2) a significant proportion of young scientists in the total number of scientific and pedagogical workers;

3) the presence of generally accepted scientific schools at the international and domestic levels; 4) sufficient number of students; 5) high level of educational services; 6) an effective system for ensuring the quality of educational activities; 7) a clear and highly effective organizational management structure of the university; 8) other.

Weaknesses of HEI: 1) insufficient level of material and technical support; 2) imperfection of the selection system for the positions of scientific and pedagogical workers; 3) imperfection of the system of housing and living conditions for students of the HEI; 4) problems of limited energy resources; 5) lack of financing of social programs; 6) other.

Opportunities for the development of HEI: 1) development of international cooperation programs; 2) introduction of modern information technologies in educational, scientific, managerial processes; 3) student self-government development; 4) infrastructure development aimed at improving housing and living conditions for students; 5) improvement of material and technical basis of scientific activity; 6) improvement of the material and technical basis of the educational process; 7) improvement of the quality of preparation for the first, second, third educational qualification levels in the context of taking into account labor market requirements; 8) an increase in the number of students, including foreign students; 9) commercialization of scientific research; 10) other.

Threats to the development of an HEI: 1) state policy regarding the formation of a training order for students; 2) increasing competition between the OIE and the market for educational services; 3) unstable demand for graduates of different areas and specialties of the law enforcement at the labor market; 4) the constantly increasing requirements for HEI, the level of preparation of students, the quality of work of the HEI; 5) reduction of state financing of HEI; 6) insufficient financing of scientific fundamental and applied research; 7) insufficient level of knowledge of foreign languages of scientific and pedagogical workers of the HEI; 8) low level of certification of scientific research results; 9) insufficient level of international publishing activity; 10) low mobility of students and scientific and pedagogical workers of HEI; 11) insufficient number of double diploma programs; 12) low number of international grants received; 13) other.

Priority strategic directions for the development of the HEI: 1) improving the quality of the scientific and pedagogical potential of the teaching staff; 2) improving the quality of education; 3) raising the level of scientific research; 4) ensuring the quality of innovation activities; 5) ensuring international recognition; 6) ensuring presence in the global information space; 7) intensification of work on the development of programs of double diplomas; 8) an increase in the number of publications and the citation index in science-based databases; 9) strengthening the research potential of the HEI; 10) ensuring internationalization of education; 11) ensuring active cooperation with the international scientific community; 12) formation of strong ties with leading and well-known foreign universities; 13) introduction and development of joint educational programs; 14) extension of double diploma programs; 15) ensuring the creation of the latest innovations and products in the field of science and technology that would reflect a real contribution to the development of the economy and society at the state and international levels; 16) achievement of international recognition; 17) other.

The main factor in assessing the quality of HEI training is employers who are able to evaluate in practice the knowledge, skills and abilities of graduates. In conducting their questionnaire survey and analysis of strategic directions and prospects of development of domestic HEI it is recommended to find out the following information:

- 1) Do employers pay attention to the fact that the graduate of higher education institution is their potential employee?
- 2) How do employers assess the quality of graduates' training for the institution of higher education (HEI)?
- 3) Specialists, which are the best practices among employers?
- 4) What factors, in the opinion of employers, contribute to the proper preparation of students of HEI?
- 5) What factors, in the opinion of employers, impede the proper preparation of students of HEI?
- 6) What is the lack of graduates of HEI, according to employers, for prestigious and high-paying employment?

When conducting a questionnaire survey of students in the context of research and analysis of strategic directions and prospects of development of domestic HEI it is advisable to find out:

- 1) What became decisive when choosing HEI?
- 2) Were there any expectations of studying at the institution of higher education?
- 3) What are the factors that make up the HEI reputation?
- 4) What is necessary to strengthen the position, increase the reputation and popularity of a specific HEI at the international level?
- 5) What are the strengths and weaknesses of a specific HEI?
- 6) What are the opportunities for the development of a specific HEI?
- 7) What are the potential threats to the development of a specific HEI?
- 8) What are the most important strategic directions for the development of a particular HEI?
- 9) Would you like to continue studying in a specific HEI at the following levels of training?
- 10) Would you recommend a specific HEI to other people for higher education?

According to the results of the conducted studies, a matrix of SWOT-analysis of the activity of domestic institutions of higher education was formed (tab. 1).

Table 1. Matrix of SWOT-analysis of activity of domestic institutions of higher education

The inner environment	
Strengths	Weaknesses
1) high qualification of scientific and scientific-pedagogical workers; 2) a significant proportion of young scientists in the total number of scientific and pedagogical workers; 3) the presence of generally accepted scientific schools at the international and domestic levels; 4) sufficient number of students; 5) high level of educational services.	1) insufficient level of material and technical support; 2) imperfection of the system of living and living conditions for students of the HEI; 3) problems of limited energy resources; 4) lack of financing of social programs.
Environment	
Opportunity	Threats
1) development of international cooperation programs; 2) introduction of modern information technologies in educational, scientific, managerial processes; 3) infrastructure development to improve housing and living conditions for students; 4) improvement of the quality of preparation for the first, second, third educational qualification levels in the context of taking into account the requirements of the labor market; 5) commercialization of scientific research.	1) state policy regarding the formation of a training order for students; 2) increasing competition between the HEI and the market for educational services; 3) unstable demand for graduates of different areas and specialties of the law enforcement at the labor market; 4) reduction of state financing of HEI; 5) insufficient funding for scientific fundamental and applied research.

Source: compiled by the authors

On the basis of the results of the research, priority strategic directions of development (functional areas of activity) of the national institutions of higher education have been identified, which should be actively pursued in the direction of further development and improvement: international positioning; educational activity and quality of education; research activities; informational support of educational process and scientific activity; material and technical support of the educational process and scientific activity; management system; social work.

Conclusions

The methodical principles of research and analysis of strategic directions and prospects of development of domestic HEI are developed. The structural-logical model of research and analysis of strategic directions and prospects of development of domestic HEI is proposed. In the context of the study, the goal, object, methods of research, the peculiarities of the formation of the sample, directions of research and analysis were determined.

For the purpose of studying and analyzing strategic directions and prospects of development of domestic HEI, it is recommended to conduct a questionnaire survey of managers of institutional level of management of HEI, employers, students.

According to the results of the study, the strengths and weaknesses, threats and opportunities of the domestic institutions of higher education were identified, which allowed the formation of a SWOT-analysis matrix.

The obtained results of the study allowed to form the necessary information support for formation of strategic directions and prospects of development of domestic institutions of higher education: international positioning; educational activity and quality of education; research activities; informational support of educational process and scientific activity; material and technical support of the educational process and scientific activity; management system; social work.

It is advisable to carry out further research in the direction of developing strategic measures and goals, specifying the system of indicators for strategic development of domestic institutions of higher education.

**The research was carried out within the framework of the implementation of the scientific theme "Formation and development of systems of scientific research in higher educational institutions" (State registration number 0117U003812).*

Abstract

Innovative principles of research and analysis of strategic directions and prospects of development of domestic institutions of higher education (IHE) are developed. For this purpose, a structural and logical model of research and analysis of strategic directions and prospects of development of domestic IHE is proposed.

The purpose (research and analysis of strategic directions and prospects of development of domestic IHE), object (domestic institutions of higher education, their activity, strategic directions and prospects of development), research methods (questionnaires, SWOT-analysis), peculiarities of sample formation, research directions and analysis were defined.

In order to form strategic directions and prospects for the development of domestic IHE, it is suggested to conduct a questionnaire survey of experts. At the same time, it is recommended that the influence of internal and external factors on the functioning of the IHE be determined by interviewing the heads of the institutional level of management of the IHE, employers and students.

The directions of research are determined, namely: the main factors of formation of reputation of IHE; generally recognized scientific schools of IHE; determinants of strategic development of IHE; strategic measures to strengthen positions in international and domestic systems for evaluating IHE; the strengths and weaknesses of the IHE; opportunities and threats of the development of the IHE; priority strategic directions of the development of IHE.

The content of each definite research direction was proposed, which provided the possibility of using the proposed innovative approach and made it possible to make the correct choice of the answer variant by the respondents determined by the survey. The main factors that can be explored and studied through the survey are identified. The list of questions, which is expediently highlighted in questionnaires for interviewing different, defined categories of respondents, is proposed.

According to the results of the study, the strengths and weaknesses, threats and opportunities of the domestic institutions of higher education were identified, which allowed the formation of a SWOT-analysis matrix.

The necessary information provision has been formed for the development of strategic directions and prospects for the development of domestic higher education institutions.

The offered innovative approach allowed to form the necessary information base for the development of strategic measures and a system of strategic indicators for the development of domestic institutions of higher education.

Список літератури:

1. Гладченко М.М. SWOT-аналіз – складова частина стратегічного менеджменту вищих навчальних закладів країн ЄС / М.М. Гладченко // Наукові записки [Національного педагогічного університету ім. М.П. Драгоманова]. Серія: Педагогічні та історичні науки. – 2013. – Вип. 109. – С. 33-40. – Режим доступу: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Nzped_2013_109_7.
2. Покришка Л. SWOT-аналіз діяльності навчального закладу на прикладі Технічного коледжу Тернопільського національного технічного університету імені Івана Пулюя / Л. Покришка // Збірник тез X Всеукраїнської студентської науково-технічної конференції «Природничі та гуманітарні науки. Актуальні питання», 25-26 квітня 2017 року. – Т.: ТНТУ, 2017. – Том 1. – С. 73-74.
3. Ярмош О.В. Система показників моніторингу стратегії розвитку вищих навчальних закладів / О.В. Ярмош / I Международная научно-практическая Интернет-конференция «Актуальные вопросы повышения конкурентоспособности государства, бизнеса и образования в современных экономических условиях» (Полтава, 14-15 февраля 2013г.). – Режим доступу: http://www.confcontact.com/20130214_econ/4_yarmosh.htm.
4. Шевченко Л.С. Сучасний університет: формування суспільної репутації / Л.С. Шевченко // Сучасні тенденції та актуальні питання соціально-економічного розвитку підприємств: матеріали міжнар. наук.-практ. конф., тези доп. – Х.: ХНУБА, 2013. – Ч. 1. – С. 275–280.
5. Пономарчук Н. Використання SWOT-аналізу для просування освітніх послуг на регіональному ринку / Н. Пономарчук // Екон. аналіз. – 2009. – Вип. 4. – С. 62-64.
6. Піняк І. Репутація вищого навчального закладу як маркетинговий інтелектуальний актив / І. Піняк / Матеріали шостої Всеукраїнської науково-практичної конференції «Інноваційний розвиток: стратегічний погляд у майбутнє» ТНТУ імені Івана Пулюя, (Тернопіль, 8 квітня 2017 року). – С. 45-46 [Електронний ресурс]. – Режим доступу: http://elartu.tntu.edu.ua/bitstream/lib/21347/2/IRSP_2017_Pinyak_I-The_reputation_of_the_higher_45-46.pdf.
7. Тоцька О.Л. SWOT-аналіз системи вищої освіти в Україні / О.Л. Тоцька // Науковий вісник Волинського національного університету ім. Лесі Українки / Волин. нац. ун-т ім. Лесі Українки; редкол.: Л.Г. Ліпич [та ін.]. – Луцьк, 2012. – № 5(230): Економічні науки. – С. 41-46. – Бібліогр.: с. 45-46.
8. Martin M. Constructing an indicator system or scorecard for higher education [Електронний ресурс] / Michaela Martin, Claude Sauvageo . – France: International Institute for Educational Planning, 2011. – 90 p. – Режим доступу: <http://www.unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0018/001824/182453e.pdf>.
9. Singh B., Grover S., Singh V. (2013) An overview of benchmarking process: the continuous improvement tool. Int J YMCAUST 1(2):80–83.
10. Anand G., Kodali R. (2008). Benchmarking the benchmarking models. Benchmarking 15(3):257–291.
11. Hinton M., Francis G., Holloway J. (2000). Best practice benchmarking in the UK. Benchmarking 7(1):52–61.
12. Gourishankar V., Sai Lokachari P. (2012). Benchmarking educational development efficiencies of the Indian states: a DEA approach. Int J Educ Manag 26(1):99–130.
13. Koller M., Salzberger T. (2009). Benchmarking in service marketing—a longitudinal analysis of the customer. Benchmarking 16(3):401–414.

14. Проект. Програма розвитку Національного університету «Львівська політехніка» на період до 2020 року. – Львів. – 2010 р.
15. Програма розвитку Київського національного університету імені Тараса Шевченка на 2012-2020 роки [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: http://science.univ.kiev.ua/documents/rozvytok/Progran_Univ_2020.pdf.
16. Концепція освітньої діяльності Національного технічного університету «Харківський політехнічний інститут» на 2016-2025 роки [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <http://public.kpi.kharkov.ua/wp-content/uploads/2016/02/razvitie-proekt.pdf>.
17. Стратегія розвитку НТУУ «КПІ» на 2012-2020 роки (концептуальні положення) та план дій щодо її виконання / Уклад.: Ю.І. Якименко, М.Ю. Льченко, Г.Б. Варламов та ін.; під заг. ред. М.З. Згуровського. – К.: НТУУ «КПІ», 2012. – 44 с. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <http://dpr.kpi.ua/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/Strategiya-rozvitku-NTUU-KPI-na-2012-2020-roki.pdf>.
18. Програма розвитку Харківського національного університету імені В.Н. Каразіна на 2010-2020 роки [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <http://www.univer.kharkov.ua/docs/polozhennya/program2010-2020nw.pdf>.
19. Концепція стратегічного розвитку Дніпропетровського національного університету імені Олеся Гончара на 2011-2017 роки [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: http://www.dnu.dp.ua/view/statut_universitetu.
20. Концептуальні засади діяльності Сумського державного університету, стратегія розвитку на 2010-2020 роки, заходи реалізації та прогнози показники (оновлена редакція) [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <http://sumdu.edu.ua/ukr/general/normative-base.html?task=getfile&tmpl=component&id=86fb8da5-e787-e311-a3b8-001a4be6d04a&kind=1>.
21. Концепція розвитку Чернівецького національного університету імені Юрія Федьковича на 2012-2022 роки [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: http://www.chnu.edu.ua/index.php?page=ua/zaginf/04%20ofic_inf/01%20normdocs.
22. Бублик, М.І. Аналізування розвитку навчально-наукової діяльності закладів вищої освіти / М.І. Бублик, Н.І. Дуляба, Н.Я. Петришин, Х.В. Дрималовська // Економічний аналіз: зб. наук. праць / Тернопільський національний економічний університет; редкол.: О.В. Ярошук (голов. ред.) та ін. – Тернопіль: Видавничо-поліграфічний центр Тернопільського національного економічного університету «Економічна думка», 2018. – Том 28. – № 1. – С. 30-39. – ISSN 1993-0259.

References:

1. Gladchenko, M.M. (2013). SWOT analysis – an integral part of strategic management of higher education institutions of EU countries. Scientific Notes National Pedagogical University named after. MP Drahomanov, 109, 33-40. Retrieved from http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Nzped_2013_109_7 [in Ukrainian].
2. Pokrykisha, L. (2017). SWOT-analysis of the activity of the educational institution on the example of the Technical College of the Ivan Puluj Ternopil National Technical University. Collection of theses of the All-Ukrainian Student Scientific and Technical Conference "Natural and Humanitarian Sciences. Topical Issues", 1, 73-74 [in Ukrainian].
3. Yarmosh, O.V. (2013). The system of indicators for monitoring the development strategy of higher educational institutions. I International Scientific and Practical Internet Conference "Actual Issues of Increasing the Competitiveness of the State, Business and Education in Modern Economic Conditions". Retrieved from http://www.confcontact.com/20130214_econ/4_yarmosh.htm [in Ukrainian].
4. Shevchenko, L.S. (2013). Modern University: Formation of Public Reputation. Current trends and topical issues of socio-economic development of enterprises: materials intern. science-practice conf., abstract (pp. 275-280). KH.: KHNUBA [in Ukrainian].
5. Ponomarchuk, N. (2009). Use of SWOT-analysis to promote educational services in the regional market Econ. Analysis, 4, 62-64 [in Ukrainian].
6. Pinyak, I. (2017). Reputation of a higher educational institution as a marketing intellectual asset. Materials of the Sixth All-Ukrainian Scientific and Practical Conference "Innovative Development: A Strategic View to the Future" Ivan Puluj TNTU (pp. 45-46). Retrieved from http://elartu.tntu.edu.ua/bitstream/lib/21347/2/IRSP_2017_Pinyak_I-The_reputation_of_the_higher_45-46.pdf [in Ukrainian].
7. Totskaya, O.L. (2012). SWOT Analysis of the Higher Education System in Ukraine. Scientific Bulletin of the Volyn National University. Lesia Ukrainka / Volyn. nats Un-t them. Lesia Ukrainka; red. L.G. Lypych [and others.], 5 (230), 41-46 [in Ukrainian].
8. Martin, M., & Sauvageo, C. (2011). Constructing an indicator system or scorecard for higher education. France: International Institute for Educational Planning. Retrieved from <http://www.unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0018/001824/182453e.pdf> [in English].

9. Singh, B., Grover, S., Singh, V. (2013). An overview of benchmarking process: the continuous improvement tool. *Int J YMCAUST*, 1(2), 80-83 [in English].
10. Anand, G., Kodali, R. (2008). Benchmarking the benchmarking models. *Benchmarking*, 15(3), 257-291 [in English].
11. Hinton, M., Francis, G., Holloway, J. (2000). Best practice benchmarking in the UK. *Benchmarking*, 7(1), 52-61 [in English].
12. Gourishankar, V., Sai Lokachari, P. (2012). Benchmarking educational development efficiencies of the Indian states: a DEA approach. *Int J Educ Manag*, 26(1), 99-130 [in English].
13. Koller, M., Salzberger, T. (2009). Benchmarking in service marketing – a longitudinal analysis of the customer. *Benchmarking*, 16(3), 401-414 [in English].
14. Project. The program of development of the National University "Lviv Polytechnic" for the period till 2020. Lviv, 2010 [in Ukrainian].
15. Program of development of Kyiv National Taras Shevchenko University for 2012-2020. Retrieved from: http://science.univ.kiev.ua/documents/rozvytok/Progran_Univ_2020.pdf [in Ukrainian].
16. Concept of educational activity of the National Technical University "Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute" for 2016-2025. Retrieved from <http://public.kpi.kharkov.ua/wp-content/uploads/2016/02/razvitiye-project.pdf> [in Ukrainian].
17. Yakimenko, Yu.I., Ilchenko, M.Yu., Varlamov, G.B., Zgurovsky, M.Z. (2012). Strategy of development of NTUU "KPI" for 2012-2020 (conceptual provisions) and action plan on its implementation. K.: NTUU "KPI", 2012. Retrieved from <http://dpr.kpi.ua/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/Strategiya-rozvitku-NTUU-KPI-na-2012-2020-roki.pdf> [in Ukrainian].
18. Program of development of Kharkiv National University named after V.N. Karazin for 2010-2020. Retrieved from <http://www.univer.kharkov.ua/docs/polozhennya/program2010-2020nw.pdf> [in Ukrainian].
19. Concept of strategic development of Oles Honchar Dnipropetrovsk National University for 2011-2017. Retrieved from http://www.dnu.dp.ua/view/statut_universitetu [in Ukrainian].
20. Conceptual basis of activity of Sumy State University, development strategy for 2010-2020, implementation measures and forecast indicators (updated version). Retrieved from <http://sumdu.edu.ua/ukr/general/normative-base.html?task=getfile&tmpl=component&id=86fb8da5-e787-e311-a3b8-001a4be6d04a&kind=1> [in Ukrainian].
21. Concept of development of Yuriy Fedkovych Chernivtsi National University for 2012-2022. Retrieved from http://www.chnu.edu.ua/index.php?page=ua/zaginf/04%20ofic_inf/01%20normdocs [in Ukrainian].
22. Bublyk, M.I., Dulyaba, N.I., Petryshyn, N.Ya., & Drimalovskaya, K.V. (2018). Analysis of the development of educational and scientific activity of institutions of higher education. *Economic Analysis: Sb. sciences works*. Ternopil National Economic University; Editorial: O.V. Yaroshchuk (head ed.) and others. Ternopil: Publishing and Printing Center of Ternopil National Economic University "Economic Thought", 28(1), 30-39 [in Ukrainian].

Посилання на статтю:

Bublyk M. I. Methodical bases of research and analysis of strategic directions and prospects for development of domestic institutions of higher education / M. I. Bublyk, L. V. Zhuk, N. Ya. Petryshyn, N. I. Duliaba // Економічний журнал Одеського політехнічного університету. – 2018. – № 3 (5). – С. 5-12. – Режим доступу до журн.: <https://economics.opu.ua/ejopu/2018/No3/5.pdf>. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2351163.

Reference a Journal Article:

Bublyk M. I. Methodical bases of research and analysis of strategic directions and prospects for development of domestic institutions of higher education / M. I. Bublyk, L. V. Zhuk, N. Ya. Petryshyn, N. I. Duliaba // Economic journal Odessa polytechnic university. – 2018. – № 3 (5). – С. 5-12. – Retrieved from <https://economics.opu.ua/ejopu/2018/No3/5.pdf>. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2351163.

